

Chemical Approaches to Penicillin Allergy-I The Syntheses of Polymeric Chains containing the Structural Elements of Benzyl Penicillin for sequestering the Penicillin-receptor Protein and Antibody

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The syntheses of six different Polymers in which the structural elements of Penicillin G were grafted onto Polystyrene Backbones are reported. Three of these Polymers TF-1, TF-2 and TF-3 had the Phenyl end of Penicillin G attached to the Polymeric Backbone through Para position with different chain lengths separating the Penicillyl Residues from the Backbone. In the other three Polymers HF-1, HF-2 and HF-3 Benzyl Penicillin Residues were grafted onto Polymeric Benzyl Alcohols through the Carboxyl Groups keeping the Phenyl end free.

The HF-1 Polymer has been used to sequester a specific receptor for Penicillin from allergic rabbit serum and can be detached from the column as Penicilloylated Protein by Hydrogenolysis. A protein having antibody properties has been isolated from the 2 M Thiourea Eluates from the TF-3 Polymer.

THE allergic reactions are generally accepted as a special class of antigen-antibody reactions.

There are two prevalent theories regarding the nature of the antigen which initiates the immunological sequence in penicillin allergy. Stewart et al^{1,2} hold that the polymeric impurities including protein bound penicillin which are present in commercial penicillin preparations serve as antigens in sensitive subjects. Levine, deWeck and others on the other hand found that penicillin molecule itself or its low molecular weight degradation products such as penicillenic-penicilloic, penilloic and penamaldic acid can serve as haptenic determinants.^{3,4}

Recent studies by Locher et al⁵, Schneider⁶, and Grant⁷ show that almost all the immunogenic reactions in rabbits with artificially induced penicillin-

allergy reactions can be explained on the basis of polymeric impurities. However, in these experiments it was not conclusively established that the smaller molecules such as penicillin or its possible degradation products at physiological pH conditions do not elicit any allergic response.

In involving a small molecule which has haptenic properties in the antigenic system one has to assume that a larger molecule such as a protein should be firmly associated with such small molecules to bring the molecular weight to the minimum size of 35,000-40,000 to function as the full fledged antigen. However, the concentrations of such a protein—the “penicillin receptor” are likely to be too small in the serum of sensitive animals or patients for isolation of such proteins by the conventional techniques. Only minute traces of allergens can induce allergy in sensitive subjects.

To investigate such systems, therefore, one has to devise special strategies. The present communication

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deals with highly specific polymeric systems of penicillin which have been successfully used to sequester minute quantities of receptor protein as well as the antibody.

The strategy was based on assumption that although many proteins are known to bind with penicillin or proteins from sera are likely to bind to penicillin, the specific binding of the receptor and penicillin is likely to be the strongest and more likely to be a co-valent one. The possibility also exists of a strongly non-covalent association of a "receptor" with hydrophobic and hydrophilic interactions. The plan, therefore, was to present the structural elements of benzyl penicillin to the proteins from sera of sensitive animals, in the form of insoluble polymers and strip out the proteins which are not covalently bonded from the polymers with reagents of graded denaturing ability to obtain a series of desorbed proteins. For the covalently bonded proteins the polymers were so designed as to detach the penicillin-bound proteins along with the penicilloyl moieties by hydrogenolysis. (Fig. 6).

Unlike the principle of affinity columns where the binding groups are attached to basically hydrophilic backbones such as agarose or sepharose, the penicillin-polymers were designed to have hydrophobic backbones such as polymethylene chains because of two reasons:—

1. The hydrophobic backbones are expected to have lesser amount of binding potentials for water-encased globular proteins, and
2. They are more easily accessible to the synthetic procedure followed and are more resistant to chemical attack particularly by acidic reagents which affect the carbohydrate-bound polymers.

The polymers were also designed to have different chain lengths separating the polymeric backbones from the haptenic penicillin moieties binding the proteins allowing progressively greater freedom to the binding protein to engulf the penicillin moieties. One hypothetical advantage of having the haptenic group close to the backbone would be the expected case of stripping the protein in the elution stage from less stronger or more constrained binding positions.

In order to have adequate space for protein binding the columns were designed to carry one penicillin moiety per ten polystyrene units.

Synthesis of Polymers : Two types of polymers (A) those with the carboxyl end of the penicillin moiety free and the bonding to polymeric backbone through the phenyl group and (tail-free polymers) and (B) those in which the carboxyl end of penicillin bonded to the polymer backbone through a benzylic hydroxyl group with the phenyl end free (head-free polymers) were synthesised. (Fig. 1).

FIG. 1

Polymer TF-1 was synthesised from chloromethylated polystyrene (2-4% cross-linked containing 1% chlorine) (I) which was converted to the nitrile (II) by refluxing with potassium cyanide in methyl cellosolve for 48 h. The nitrile (II) was hydrolysed to the acid (III) by potassium hydroxide and converted to the acid chloride (IV) by phosphorus trichloride. Finally, the polymeric structure TF-1 was elaborated by the reaction of IV with 6-amino penicillanic acid (V) (Fig. 2). The synthesis was monitored at every stage by elementary analyses and neutral equivalent (exchange capacity at the carboxyl stage). The yields in terms of penicillin moieties attached to the polymer was approximately one residue per every ten styrene units or based on chlorine in I ca 90%.

Polymer TF-2 with a 5-unit chain length separating the backbone from the penicillin unit was synthesised from commercial "crystalline" polystyrene (8% cross linked) (VI) by succinylation at *p*-position with succinic anhydride-aluminum chloride. The acid (VII) was converted to the acid chloride (VIII) which was condensed with *p*-amino phenyl acetic acid⁸ (IX) to give the amide (X). The carboxyl end of X was converted to the acid chloride and condensed with 6-aminopenicillanic acid (V) to yield polymer TF-2. This polymer also contained one active side chain per ten polystyrene-regulated through the stoichiometry of the succinylation reaction (Fig. 3).

SYNTHESIS OF POLYMER TF-1

Fig. 2.

SYNTHESIS OF POLYMER TF-2

FIG. 3

Polymer TF-3 was also synthesised by a sequence of reactions parallel to that for TF-2 involving the acid chloride of half ester of adipic acid (XI) at the Friedel Craft stage (Fig. 4). The polymeric keto-

ester (XII) was hydrolysed to XIII, condensed with X through the acid chloride to yield XIV on which the 6-amino-penicillanic moiety was grafted by the usual techniques.

SYNTHESIS OF POLYMER TF-3

FIG. 4

For the "head-free" polymers P-aminobenzyl alcohol (XVI) was attached to the polymeric backbones and grafted on to the carboxyl end of benzyl penicillin (XVII) using dicyclohexyl carbodiimide as the condensing agent.

For polymer HF-1 the chloromethylated polystyrene (I) was solvolysed in methyl cellosolve-water with potassium acetate followed by the hydrolysis of the polymeric acetate to the benzyl alcohol (XVIII). For HF-2 and HF-3 para amino benzyl alcohol⁹ (IX) moieties were grafted on to the acid chlorides, (VIII) and (XIV), to yield XX and XXI which were esterified with penicillin to yield HF-2 and HF-3.

All the polymers showed the presence of intact β -lactam (IR ν max. 1,775-1,780 cm^{-1}). However, it was not possible to ascertain whether any of the β -lactam-thiazolidine systems bound on polymers were degraded during the washing up procedure or during the biological experiments.

Biological experiments with penicillin polymers : The details of the immunization techniques and the methodology will be published elsewhere. Four adult rabbits, one male and three females were made allergic to penicillin by injecting penicillin with

Freunds' complete adjuvant in the foot pad at intervals of 3 to 7 days for a period of 10 weeks. The three female rabbits developed high antibody titers (600, 1,200 and 1,200 dilution units in haemagglutination tests). The male rabbit did not show any response to penicillin.

The penicillin binding proteins were sequestered by all the six polymers with different efficiency by mechanically stirring them with the sera from the rabbits. The adsorbed proteins were successively eluted with 2 M phosphate buffer of pH 7.4, 2 M thiourea and 8 M urea. Most of the studies were conducted with tail-free polymers and the head-free polymer HF-1 from which the residual co-valently bonded protein was hydrogenolysed by Pt and H_2 (Fig. 6).

The hydrogenolysed fraction moved as a single band in polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis and gave a precipitin band with unfractionated antisera from rabbits without added penicillin (Plate I) in Ochterlony plates.

The 2 M thiourea fraction from the TF-3 polymer also moved as a single band in polyacrylamide gel

SYNTHESES OF POLYMERS HF-1, HF-2 & HF-3.

FIG. 5

electrophoresis. With added penicillin the electrophoretic mobility of this fraction showed a considerable change indicating that it has a binding capacity for penicillin. It responded to the haemagglutination reaction indicating that it may be a specific antibody for penicillin antigen having a hapten-specific site (Plate. II & III).

Experimental

The I R spectra was taken on a Perkin Elmer I R 700. Polystyrene (crystalline) was a generous gift

from M/S Unichem Laboratories. Crystalline Potassium Penicillin G was a generous gift from M/S HAL, Pimpri. Samples of 6-amino-penicillenic acid (6 APA) were obtained as generous gifts from HAL, Pimpri and Cipla Laboratories, Bombay. For determination of neutral equivalents or ion-exchange capacities the following general procedure was followed :

A known weight of the polymer was stirred with a known volume of standard sodium hydroxide. The

ADSORPTION, BINDING AND RELEASE OF
RECEPTOR ON AND FROM POLYMER HF-1

FIG. 6

PLATE I. Precipitin bands shown (arrow) by the hydrogenolysed penicillin antigen (a) from HF-1 column. C is control (Phosphate buffer wash from the column). ab—unfractionated antibody.

PLATE II. Electrophoretic mobility of the 2 M thiourea fraction from TF-3 polymer after incubation with penicillin in polyacrylamide gel.

PLATE III. Electrophoretic mobility of the same fraction with-

polymer was filtered and the excess alkali back titrated against standard hydrochloric acid.

The calculated Neut. equiv. were based on 1 unit -COOH per ten units of polystyrene containing 1 active residue.

Synthesis of TF-1: Merrifield resin (10 g.) (Koch-Light & Co) (Polymer I) and Potassium cyanide (23 g.) in 2-methoxy ethanol (300 ml.) was refluxed for 4 days, under anhydrous conditions. The mixture was cooled, filtered, washed with water (1) and methanol (50 ml.) and dried. Yield of polymer II (9.8g.)

Hydrolysis of II to the polymeric phenyl acetic acid (III): Polymer II (0.75 g.) was refluxed with KOH (0.35 g.) in methoxy ethanol (10 ml.) for 4 days. The mixture was cooled, filtered, washed with 1 N hydrochloric acid, water and acetone. Yield of polymer (0.98 g.)

Neutral equivalent 0.00945 moles of carboxyl per mole of polymer (III).

Acid chloride of Polymer (III): Polymer (III) (1 g.) was treated with phosphorous trichloride (2 ml.) and dry benzene (25 ml.). The mixture was refluxed for 64 h. Excess phosphorous trichloride and benzene were removed under vacuum and the acid chloride washed with ethanol free dry acetone. Yield of polymer IV (1.12 g.)

Coupling of polymer (IV) with 6-amino penicillanic acid: Polymer (IV) (1 g.) was added to 6-amino penicillanic acid (0.1 g.) dissolved in dry dimethyl formamide (20 ml.) Sodium bicarbonate (0.1 g.) was added to the above mixture which was magnetically stirred for 48 h, washed with water and dried with acetone. Yield of polymer (TF-1) (1.31 g.). Found: C, 81.4; H, 7.2; N, 1.37; S, 1.22%. Calcd: C, 80.2; H, 6.9; N, 1.41; S, 1.31%.

Preparation of HF-1: Conversion of Merrifield resin (polymer I) to the acetate.

Polymer (I) (5.0 g.) and potassium acetate (1.4 g.) were refluxed in methyl cellosolve (40 ml.) for 64 h. The mixture was cooled, washed with water and dried. Yield of polymer (5.2 g.).

Hydrolysis of Polymer: The polymeric benzyl acetate (5.2 g.) was refluxed with 0.5 M NaOH (30 ml.) for 48 h. The mixture was cooled, filtered and washed

with water and methanol and dried. Yield of polymer XVIII (5.1 g.).

Coupling of polymer (XVIII) with potassium benzyl penicillin (V): Polymer (XVIII) (0.5 g.) was added to a solution of penicillin G-K (0.18 g.) and 1-ethyl-3-(3-dimethyl amino propyl)-carbodiimide hydrochloride (0.11 g.) in 10 ml. distilled water. The solution was stirred for 72 h. and washed with water and dried. Yield of HF-1 (0.73 g.). Found: C, 83.4; H, 7.3; N, 1.32; S, 1.12%. Calcd: C, 82.9; H, 7.1; N, 1.36; S, 1.21%.

Succinoylation of Polystyrene: Polystyrene (5 g.) was dissolved in 45 ml. of nitrobenzene. Succinic anhydride (0.5 g.) was added and the mixture was stirred till it became homogeneous. Aluminium chloride (1.5 g.) was added to the solution keeping the temperature between 0-10°C. It was then stirred at room temperature for a further 2 h. and allowed to stand at room temperature overnight. The mixture was then poured into excess of 8 N hydrochloric acid and the nitrobenzene steam distilled.

The resulting polymer (VII) was characterised by titrating the -CO₂H groups. The results of the titration indicated that 0.044 moles of carboxyl groups per mole of polystyrene was present. Calcd:— 0.042 moles under of -CO₂H per mole of polymer.

Acid chloride of Succinoylated polystyrene: Succinoylated polystyrene (2.5 g.) (VII) was treated with 2 ml. of phosphorous trichloride in 25 ml. dry benzene and refluxed for 48 h. Excess benzene and phosphorous trichloride were removed under vacuum. The resulting acid chloride (VIII) was washed with ethanol-free dry acetone and dried in a vac. desiccator. Yield (2.8 g.).

Condensation of VIII with IX: VIII (5 g.) was treated in 25 ml. dry acetone with *p*-amino-phenyl acetic acid⁸(IX) (0.98 g.). Fused potassium carbonate (1.5 g.) was then added to the reaction mixture and the mixture refluxed for 16 h. Excess acetone and *p*-amino-phenyl acetic acid were removed by washing with water and the product X dried. Yield 5.8 g. Found: Neutral Equivalents 0.039 moles. Found: N, 2.53; H, 8.1; C, 80.91%. Calcd: N, 2.38; H, 8.23; C, 81.01% Calcd: Neutral Equivalents of -CO₂H per mole of polymer -0.037 moles.

Acid chloride of polymer X: Polymer X (5 g.) was treated with phosphorous trichloride (2.5 ml.) in 25 ml. dry benzene and the mixture refluxed for 16 h

Excess benzene and phosphorous trichloride removed under suction. The acid chloride was washed with ethanol free dry acetone. Yield (6.2 g.)

Condensation of Acid chloride with 6 APA (V) : To the above acid chloride (6 g.) in dry pyridine (20 ml.) was added 3.3 g. of 6-amino penicillanic acid. The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 24 h. The excess pyridine was removed by washing with large volumes of ethanol. The resulting polymer TF-2 was dried and weighed 8.1 g. Found : N, 3.29 ; H, 8.29 ; C, 81.03 % Calcd. N, 3.21 ; H, 8.30 ; C, 81.12%.

Synthesis of Polymer HF-2 : Polymer VIII (5 g.) was taken in 30 ml. dry acetone and *p*-amino benzyl alcohol⁹ (1 g.) and fused pot. carbonate (1.5 g.) was added to the mixture which was refluxed for 16 h. The polymer (XVIII) was washed with water and dried. Yield (5.8 g.). Found : N, 2.69 ; H, 7.1 ; C, 81.1%. Calcd. : N, 2.58 ; H, 6.9 ; C, 80.9%.

Condensation of Polymer (XVIII) with benzyl penicillin : XVII (5 g.) was taken in 30 ml. dry dimethyl formamide and treated with dicyclohexylcarbodiimide (1.8 g.). Potassium penicillin G (3.5) was added to the mixture in one lot and the mixture stirred for 24 h. Dicyclohexyl-urea formed during the reaction was removed by washing with large volumes of ethanol. Yield of HF-2 polymer 1.8 g. Found : N, 2.70 ; H, 6.19 ; C, 83.1%. Calcd : N, 2.6 ; H, 6.3 ; C, 82.3%.

Preparation of Ethyl chloroadipate (XI) : A modified synthesis of the one reported by E. E. Blaise and A. Kochler¹⁰ was adopted for improved yields.

Adipic acid (10 g.) was treated with ethanol (42 ml.) and conc. H₂SO₄ (6 ml.) and refluxed for 6 h. Concentrated aqueous potassium bicarbonate solution was poured into the reaction mixture till a pH of 4.0-5.0 was reached. The oil that separated was extracted with ether and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. After removal of the solvent the crude product (9.5 g.) (I R ν max. 1,730, 1,720, broad peak 3,100-3,300 cm⁻¹) was refluxed directly with thionyl chloride (9 ml) for 2 h. and the excess thionyl chloride removed under vacuum. The resulting acid chloride was distilled in vacuum—boiling point 110°C at 4 mm. Yield 6.4 g. (I R ν max. 1,790, 1,730 cm⁻¹).

Friedel Crafts reaction of polystyrene with ethyl chloro adipate : Polystyrene (31.5 g.) was dissolved in 250 ml. of dry nitrobenzene and the solution cooled

to 1-10°C and treated with ethyl chloro adipate (6.2 g.). Anhydrous aluminium chloride (7 g.) was added to the solution with constant stirring, maintaining the temperature between 0-10°C. After the initial reaction subsided in the ice bath the solution was stirred at room temperature for a further 2 h. when the resulting solution turned into a viscous deep red liquid. It was left overnight to complete the reaction. The reaction mixture was poured into excess 1:1 dil. hydrochloric acid and the excess nitrobenzene was steam distilled. The final product appeared as a brittle white solid. Yield (40 g.)

Hydrolysis of the ester : The above polymer (XII) was hydrolyzed by refluxing with 250 ml. of 8 N HCL for 16 h.

Estimation of -CO₂H groups : A known weight of the adipolyted polystyrene is stirred with a known volume of standard NaOH for half an hour. The polymer is filtered and washed with water. The excess NaOH in the filtrate is titrated against standard HCL. From the quantity of the NaOH consumed the number of carboxyl groups is determined. Found : 0.08 moles of CO₂H per mole of polymer. Calcd : 0.69 moles of -CO₂H per mole of polymer.

Preparation of the acid chloride of adipoylated polystyrene : The adipoylated polystyrene (XII) (10 g.) and phosphorous trichloride (7 ml.) were refluxed in dry benzene for 48 h. Excess of benzene and phosphorous trichloride were removed under reduced pressure. The acid chloride was washed with ethanol-free dry acetone, dried in a vacuum desiccator and weighed. Yield (11.2 g.).

Condensation of acid chloride with p-amino benzyl alcohol : The above acid chloride was taken in dry acetone (60 ml.) and *p*-amino benzyl alcohol (1.8 g.) was added. Fused potassium carbonate was added and the mixture refluxed for 16 h.

The excess potassium carbonate was washed with water and the polymer dried by washing with acetone and subsequently in a vacuum desiccator. Yield (12.2 g.). Found : C, 88.6 ; H, 7.10 ; N, 1.40%. Calcd : C, 89.4 ; H, 7.65 ; N, 1.35%.

To a suspension of the above polymer (12.2 g.) taken in dry dimethyl formamide (100 ml.), dicyclohexyl carbodiimide (3.6 g.) and potassium penicillin G (7.6 g.) were added. The mixture was stirred at room temp. for 24 h. and the excess of DCCI if any, was decomposed by adding water.

The dicyclohexyl urea formed during the reaction was removed by stirring with an excess of alcohol. Yield (16.4 g.). Found : N, 3.5 ; H, 2.5 ; C, 83.6. Calcd : N, 3.2 ; H, 2.42 ; C, 84%.

Condensation of XIV with p-amino phenyl acetic acid : XIV (11.2 g.) was taken in 60 ml. dry acetone and treated with *p*-amino-phenyl acetic acid and fused potassium carbonate (3.0 g.) and the mixture refluxed for 16 h, cooled, filtered and freed from the excess acetone and potassium carbonate by washing with water. Yield (12.4 g.). Found : 0.0424 moles of $-CO_2H$ per mole of polymer. Found : N, 2.53 ; H, 7.4 ; C, 83.2% ; Calcd : N, 2.39 ; H, 7.43 ; C, 82.9%. Calcd : 0.037 moles of $-CO_2H$ per mole of polymer.

Acid chloride of the above polymer : XV (12.4 g.) was refluxed in benzene (50 ml.) and phosphorous trichloride (5 ml.) for 16 h. Excess benzene and phosphorous trichloride were removed under reduced pressure and the acid chloride washed with ethanol-free dry acetone and dried in a vacuum desiccator. Yield (13.8 g.).

Condensation of the acid chloride with 6 APA : The acid chloride (13.5 g.) was taken in dry pyridine (50 ml.) and 6 APA (7 g.) was added. The mixture was stirred at room temp. for 24 h. and the excess pyridine was washed with a large volume of ethanol. The polymer was dried in a vacuum desiccator and weighed. Yield (17.1 g.). Found : N, 3.2 ; H, 6.9 ; C, 84.6%. Calcd : N, 3.43 ; H, 7.1 ; C, 84.2%.

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The original method gave poor yields. In later experiments *p*-amino benzyl alcohol was prepared by lithium aluminium hydride reduction of *p*-amino-methyl benzoate in dry ether in 70% yield.